

DENT RESISTANCE OF HYBRID COMPOSITE/METAL LAMINATES FOR LIGHTWEIGHT AUTOMOTIVE BODY STRUCTURES

B M Weager, C D Rudd, M J Clifford
University of Nottingham, UK

C F Johnson
Ford Motor Company, USA

ABSTRACT

Thermoplastic matrix composites are thought to have many potential applications in the automotive industry, specifically to reduce vehicle weight and manufacturing cost. The adoption of composite components into predominantly metallic body structures presents a number of problems for automotive manufacturers. These include the difficulties of joining and surface quality. Hybrid laminates of thermoplastic composite and a sheet metal skin can yield significant weight reduction, while utilising existing spot-welding and painting technology. This study evaluates the dent resistance of these hybrid laminates, compared with traditional metallic automotive body materials.

The materials under investigation in this study are Twintex[®] (Vetrotex Saint-Gobain), a commingled woven glass fibre-reinforced polypropylene, GMT (Symalit), a random glass fibre-reinforced polypropylene, and standard automotive grade steel and aluminium sheet. Hybrid laminates have been prepared by non-isothermal compression moulding of pre-heated material stacks. Composite/metal adhesion has been achieved by surface pre-treatment of the metal and incorporation of a modified polymer at the composite/metal interface. A series of specimens with different composite/metal ratios have been produced at equivalent flexural stiffness to the metallic sheet. Flexural behaviour has been assessed by three-point bend testing.

Quasi-static dent resistance testing has been performed on a universal testing machine. Flat coupon specimens were clamped in a circular test rig and incrementally loaded with a hemispherical indenter. Dent depth was measured using an LVDT. The hybrid laminates performed favourably compared to traditional metallic body materials. Denting of the metal skin is thought to be suppressed by the elastic response of the thermoplastic composite.

Key terms: dent resistance, hybrid, composite, metal, laminate.

INTRODUCTION

Fibre-reinforced polymers have been used to reduce the weight of automotive body structures for many years. Recent attention has focussed on thermoplastic-based composites, as these have advantages in rapid manufacturing and recyclability. Glass-reinforced polypropylene (PP) is of particular interest due to its relatively low cost. However, being a polyolefin, PP is difficult to join, and its high contraction on cooling results in poor surface quality. To overcome these problems, hybrid laminates of thermoplastic composite and sheet metal are under development,

whereby the composite reduces panel weight and the metal skin aids joining and improves surface finish. These materials may also offer improved dent performance over traditional body materials.

Dent resistance is a key property for automotive body panels, which are generally present for aesthetic rather than structural reasons. Outer body panels must be resilient to static loads, such as a person leaning on the car, and dynamic loads, such as stone impact. Dent resistance is considered to be a function of yield strength, thickness, panel shape/radii of curvature (all proportional to dent resistance), and modulus of elasticity (inversely proportional to dent resistance) [1]. It may be defined simply as the resistance of a panel to plastic or permanent deformation [2]. There are no standard test methods for assessing dent resistance, so automotive manufacturers tend to use a variety of simple tests developed in-house. The literature suggests that dent resistance is most commonly assessed quasi-statically [1-3]; fewer workers have investigated dynamic denting [4]. The majority of work reported has been conducted on metal panels pressed into various arbitrary curvatures, making cross-comparisons difficult.

Asnafi et al [3] compared the dent resistance of metal panels with that of a stainless steel/woven glass-PP laminate. They reported that a 2/1 lay-up (metal/composite/metal) performed well compared to aluminium, however, a 1/1 lay-up (metal/composite) performed poorly due to low intrinsic stiffness. In the current study, a range of panels were produced with various metal/composite ratios but equal flexural stiffness. In order to make future comparisons possible, flat panels were manufactured so the results represent a conservative estimate of dent resistance.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

Several materials were investigated in this study, as summarised in Table 1. As metallic body materials are supplied in one gauge thickness only, a range of thicknesses were obtained by abrasive lapping. To obtain satisfactory adhesion between composite and metal, the metals were surface-treated and a modified polypropylene adhesive film (XAF 23.101-40g/m², Sarna Xiro) of thickness 0.15mm was incorporated at the interface. Previous investigations [5] have shown that suitable surface-treatments are zinc phosphating for steel and sulphuric acid anodising for aluminium. The aluminium was age-hardened using a typical automotive paint-baking cycle.

Material	Grade	Delivered thickness (mm)	Typical applications	Supplier
Steel	DC04/05	0.8	Outer body strip	Corus
Aluminium	6111-T4 (+age)	0.9	Outer body strip	Alcan
Woven glass-PP	Twintex [®] 1-1 (60% glass)	0.5	Bumper beams, load floors	Saint Gobain Vetrotex
Random glass-PP	GMT (40% glass)	4	Front ends, seat structures	Symalit

Table 1. Materials under investigation.

To be able to make valid comparisons between the test specimens, a range of 1/1 lay-up panels were produced with different metal and composite thicknesses at equal flexural stiffness to the monolithic steel and aluminium (Table 2). The thickness of composite required to achieve equal flexural stiffness was calculated for a variety of metal thicknesses, based on the different elastic moduli and the distance from the neutral axis [6]. The flexural stiffness of each moulded panel was checked by three-point bend testing, according to test standard ISO 14125:1998.

No.	Metal	Composite	Metal thickness, t_m (mm)	Composite thickness, t_c (mm)	Total thickness, t (mm)*	Composite/metal ratio	Superficial density (kg/m^2)
1	Steel	-	0.8	-	0.8	0	6.3
2	Steel	Woven glass-PP	0.7	0.50	1.35	0.72	6.4
3	Steel	Woven glass-PP	0.4	1.01	1.56	2.54	4.8
4	Steel	Random glass-PP	0.7	0.73	1.58	1.05	6.6
5	Steel	Random glass-PP	0.4	1.35	1.90	3.38	5.1
6	Steel	Random glass-PP	0.3	1.46	1.91	4.88	4.4
7	Aluminium	-	0.9	-	0.9	0	2.5
8	Aluminium	Woven glass-PP	0.68	0.51	1.33	0.75	2.7
9	Aluminium	Woven glass-PP	0.23	0.98	1.35	4.34	2.2
10	Aluminium	Random glass-PP	0.68	0.72	1.55	1.07	2.9
11	Aluminium	Random glass-PP	0.45	1.02	1.62	2.26	2.7
12	Aluminium	Random glass-PP	0.23	1.23	1.61	5.48	2.4

Table 2. Summary of test specimens produced (* includes interlayer thickness 0.15mm).

Hybrid plaques were produced by non-isothermal compression moulding of pre-heated material stacks. An R Royce 4.5kW infrared oven was used to heat the materials, which were then transferred manually to a Bradley & Turton 150 tonne hydraulic press for stamping in a flat plaque tool. The processing parameters used are summarised in Table 3, after Wakeman [7].

Processing parameter	Woven glass-PP/metal	Random glass-PP/metal
Pre-heat temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	190	200
Transfer time (s)	<10	<10
Tool temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	80	50
Moulding pressure (bar)	50	200
Time at pressure (s)	60	40

Table 3. Summary of processing parameters.

Dent resistance testing was performed on 125×125mm coupons cut from the moulded plaques. Testing was conducted on a Hounsfield H25kS universal testing machine fitted with 25kN load cell and a denting rig developed in-house, as shown in Figure 1. The denting rig consists of a \varnothing 100mm anvil and clamp and a \varnothing 25.4mm (\varnothing 1") hemispherical steel indenter (Figure 2). Incremental denting was performed on each specimen, whereby each specimen was subjected to a series of indentations of increasing displacement (e.g. up to 4mm in steps of 0.2mm). The crosshead displacement rate was set to 10mm/min. In-between each indentation, the load was removed and the permanent dent depth was measured using an LVDT displacement transducer,

situated directly under the point of indentation. These readings were compared with the crosshead displacement at the point of contact and were found to be the same within the testing range.

Viscoelastic recovery was identified in specimens containing composite, so a 5 minute pause was incorporated between dent cycles. This delay allowed for >90% of ultimate recovery which, in real terms, is within 0.01mm of the recovered dent depth. The onset of visible denting was determined, during a trial test on polished aluminium, to be 0.05mm dent depth.

After testing, cross-sectional specimens were carefully cut from selected indented specimens to examine the damage at the point of indentation. These were mounted in cold setting resin, polished to P4000 SiC grit and examined under an optical microscope.

Figure 1. Dent resistance test rig.

Figure 2. Schematic diagram of dent test.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Results from the preparatory flexural testing are summarised in Table 4. The specimens were designed to have equal flexural stiffness. However, Table 4 indicates that the actual stiffnesses differ slightly from the designed stiffness.

It is interesting to note that the dominant failure mode in flexure changes with type of composite and with ratio of composite to metal. Specimens based on woven glass-PP routinely failed by delamination of the composite/metal interface. However, specimens based on random glass-PP failed by one of two mechanisms depending on the ratio of composite to metal. Specimens with relatively low composite/metal ratios (e.g. No. 4) failed by delamination of the composite/metal interface. Conversely, at high composite/metal ratios (e.g. No's 5 and 6) tensile composite failure was dominant. The presence of longitudinal aligned fibres in the woven glass-PP increases the tensile strength compared to random glass-PP, so the interface fails preferentially. In the random glass-PP no aligned fibres are present so the composite fails in tension. The change in failure mode due to composite/metal ratio is thought to be due to the difference in shear stress through the thickness and the position of high shear compared to position of the interface.

No.	Metal	Composite	Total thickness, t (mm)	Composite/metal ratio	Flexural stiffness (Nm ²)*	Relative stiffness ⁺	Dominant failure mode	failure
1	Steel	-	0.8	0	0.213	1	-	
2	Steel	Woven glass-PP	1.36	0.73	0.188	0.88	Delamination of interface	of
3	Steel	Woven glass-PP	1.6	2.63	0.229	1.07	Delamination of interface	of
4	Steel	Random glass-PP	1.74	1.27	0.206	0.97	Delamination of interface	of
5	Steel	Random glass-PP	2	3.63	0.226	1.06	Tensile failure of matrix	of
6	Steel	Random glass-PP	2.02	5.23	0.247	1.16	Tensile failure of matrix	of
7	Aluminium	-	0.9	0	0.105	1	-	
8	Aluminium	Woven glass-PP	1.7	1.30	0.113	1.07	Delamination of interface	of
9	Aluminium	Woven glass-PP	1.73	6.02	0.112	1.07	Delamination of interface	of
10	Aluminium	Random glass-PP	1.7	1.30	0.129	1.23	Tensile failure of matrix	of
11	Aluminium	Random glass-PP	1.35	1.67	0.123	1.18	Tensile failure of matrix	of
12	Aluminium	Random glass-PP	1.4	4.56	0.120	1.14	Tensile failure of matrix	of

Table 4. Summary of results from flexural testing.

Figure 3 is a typical force-time plot from a dent resistance test (first 8 cycles only). This shows the cyclic, incremental nature of the test and the pause for viscoelastic recovery. Figure 4 is a corresponding force-displacement plot. As the indentation force increases, the permanent deformation (denting) increases, indicated by the residual displacement after unloading.

Figure 3. Typical force-time plot from dent resistance test on a hybrid laminate.

Figure 4. Typical force-displacement plot from dent resistance test on a hybrid laminate.

Graphs of permanent dent depth against indentation displacement are displayed in Figures 5 and 6, for steel and aluminium-based specimens respectively. Dent depth increases with indentation displacement for all specimens. In general, a higher displacement (or force) is required to produce a dent of a given depth in hybrid composite/metal specimens compared to monolithic metal specimens. This is true for all specimens at and above the onset of visible denting (0.05mm). The beneficial effect is thought to be due to the elastic response of the underlying composite, supporting the metal skin. Hybrid specimens with a higher composite/metal ratio require a higher indentation displacement to form a dent of a given depth. Therefore, they have improved dent resistance at in that testing range. It is also worth noting that increasing the composite/metal ratio decreases the weight of the panel (Table 2). There are no clear trends when comparing the denting performance of hybrid specimens based on woven and random glass.

Figures 7 and 8 compare the force required to produce a given dent depth (0.05mm) steel and aluminium-based specimens respectively. Generally, a higher force is required to produce the dent in hybrid composite/metal specimens compared to monolithic metal specimens, and therefore have greater dent resistance. Specimens with higher composite/metal ratios require a higher force to produce the same dent. The hybrid specimens based on aluminium generally perform slightly better than those based on steel, although the relative improvement by adding composite is greater for steel than aluminium. This is most likely explained by comparing the denting performance of the two metals; aluminium out-performs steel, although it should be noted that the aluminium has lower flexural stiffness than the steel (Table 4).

Figure 9 compares the dents in aluminium/random glass-PP specimens with increasing composite ratio, all indented to 4mm displacement (approximately 1000N). The size of the dent reduces significantly with increasing composite/metal ratio. Microscopy of cross-sections of indented specimens has revealed similar damage mechanism behaviour to that observed during flexural testing. Interfacial delamination was found in all specimens based on woven glass-PP, whereas for woven glass-PP specimens, the damage mode changed with composite/metal ratio. The

damage mechanisms present in indented steel/random glass-PP specimens are compared in Figure 10. In the 0.7mm steel/random glass-PP specimen (Figure 10a), delamination of the composite/metal interface can be seen. Note that this has occurred away from the point of indentation, due to the higher shear forces from bending. The principle damage mode in the 0.4mm steel/random glass-PP specimens (Figure 10b) is matrix failure on the tensile face (lower). This behaviour concurs with that observed during flexural testing as discussed above.

Figure 5. Graph showing change in permanent dent depth with indenting force for steel-based specimens (error bars show standard deviation).

Figure 6. Graph showing change in permanent dent depth with indenting force for aluminium-based specimens (error bars show standard deviation).

Figure 7. Force required to produce 0.05mm dent depth in steel-based specimens (error bars show standard deviation).

Figure 8. Force required to produce 0.05mm dent depth in aluminium-based specimens (error bars show standard deviation).

Figure 9. Comparison of dents in aluminium-based specimens after indentation of 4mm displacement (approximately 1000N), (a) 0.9mm aluminium, 1.94mm dent, (b) 0.68mm aluminium/random glass-PP, 1.13mm dent, (c) 0.45mm aluminium/random glass-PP, 0.96mm dent, (d) 0.23mm aluminium/random glass-PP, 0.58mm dent.

Figure 10. Micrographs of cross-section through centre of indented specimens, (a) 0.7mm steel/random glass-PP, (b) 0.4mm steel/random glass-PP.

CONCLUSIONS

- Thermoplastic composite/metal hybrid laminates have improved dent resistance over traditional metallic automotive body materials at equal flexural stiffness.
- This benefit is most likely due to the elastic response of the underlying composite.
- Dent resistance increases and weight decreases with increasing composite/metal ratio.
- The principle damage mechanism in hybrid specimens based on woven glass-PP is delamination of the composite/metal interface.
- The dominant failure mode in random glass-PP specimens changes from interfacial delamination to tensile composite failure with increasing composite/metal ratio.

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